

COMPLICATION OF DIABETES MELLITUS - URILOSTICAL DISEASE

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Purpose of the study. To study the role of diabetes mellitus (DM) as one of the risk factors for urolithiasis (UCD), to consider the epidemiology of the clinical form of the combination of ICD and DM, to identify metabolic disorders that contribute to the formation of urinary stones in diabetes.

Material and methods. The frequency of diabetes in patients with urolithiasis in the Bukhara region for 3 years, from 2021 to 2023, was studied. For this purpose, 102 patients with urolithiasis were examined in a urological hospital and preventive examinations of the urban and rural population were carried out. The medical histories and outpatient records of 1475 patients with a clinical form of a combination of diabetes and urolithiasis were studied. 427 patients had type 1 diabetes, 1048 (71.7%) had type 2 diabetes. Urinary stones were studied using infrared spectroscopy in 80 people, and by standard methods in 22. Urine pH-metry was performed in 60 patients, and a comprehensive assessment of metabolic disorders leading to the formation of urinary stones was carried out in 42 patients.

Results. It has been established that among patients with ICD, the percentage of patients with diabetes is steadily increasing, from 6.6% in 2021 to 16.2% in 2023. During medical examinations, diabetes in combination with ICD was detected in 14% of cases. Stones formed in diabetes are most often (40.2%) urate, less often (30.5%) calcium oxalate. Metabolic disorders in diabetes lead to the appearance of a sharply acidic urine reaction (pH 4.5-6.0), an increase in the level of uric acid and calcium in the blood and urine.

Additional risk factors for urolithiasis in patients with diabetes are obesity, arterial hypertension, metabolic syndrome, hypercaloric diet and others.

Conclusions. Diabetes is one of the important endogenous causes of urolithiasis.

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